

THE ROLE OF METAPHOR IN THE FORMATION OF PHRASEOLOGICAL UNITS IN ENGLISH

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Abstract : Many linguistic terms such as expressive means of language, stylistic devices, figures of speech, speech devices, tropes are frequently found in linguistic literature at present time. These concepts and means mainly set the main task of studying the semantic, structural and functional aspects of language. Metaphors, which are among such language means, play a special role in the formation of phraseological units. This article discusses the role of metaphorical transfer in the formation and development of phraseological units in the English language.

Keywords: language device, phraseological unit, linguistic unit, idiom, transfer of meaning, metaphor, stylistic device, trope, set expression

Among a number of studies devoted to the study of lexical expressive means of the language, the approach proposed by the Russian linguist I.V. Galperin according to the main layers of the language, such as phonetic, lexical and syntactic, is of particular importance. One of the most advanced classifications proposed for the study of lexical expressive means of the language, in particular their classification, was put forward by V.A. Kukhareenko, in which the author distinguishes four main groups of stylistic means:

- 1) lexical stylistic means: metaphor, metonymy, personification (revival), epithet, hyperbole (exaggeration), irony, word play, zeugma;
- 2) syntactic stylistic means: inversion, ellipsis, rhetorical question, chiasm, repetitions, parallel constructions, aposiopesis, disjunction, plural;
- 3) lexical-syntactic stylistic means: antithesis, litotes, comparison (simile), periphrasis, gradation;
- 4) graphic and phonetic stylistic devices: italics, underlining, spelling errors, hyphenation, capital letters, quotation marks, alliteration, assonance, onomatopoeia, rhyme, rhythm.

It is common knowledge that phraseology and metaphor are closely related phenomena, and the most common factor causing the formation of phraseological units is metaphor. It is worth noting that metaphor is one of the linguistic phenomena that has aroused interest among philologists since antiquity, and it has a long history of study as a trope with a transferred figurative meaning. Scholars of antiquity (Aristotle, Quintilian, and many others) interpret metaphor as the independent replacement of one word by another, based on a logically determined common feature. Aristotle, in his work "Poetics", describes the essence of metaphor as follows: "Metaphor is the transfer of a word whose meaning has changed from one type to another, or from one form to another, or transference based on proportion." Based on the synchronic principles of the approach to the study of linguistic phenomena, it can be seen that the main focus is not on linguistic processes, but on the relationships between concepts.

It is well known that metaphor is not only a linguistic tool, or a research method that allows analyzing linguistic units, but also serves as an object of study for many other disciplines, such as philosophy, logic, psychology. Speaking about the various properties of metaphor, G.N. Sklyarevskaya in her monograph distinguishes 11 research directions on linguistic metaphor, including semasiological, onomasiological, epistemological, logical, linguistic, psycholinguistic, expressional, linguistic-literary, lexicological and lexicographic. In modern linguistics, it is appropriate to recall another cognitive aspect of metaphor. In particular, the famous linguists J. Lakoff and M. Johnson pay special attention to this aspect of metaphor. The authors also take into account the linguistic aspects of metaphor, including the

following sentences in the work *Metaphors We Live by*: “For many, metaphor is a means of poetic imagination and rhetorical flourishing, which is a matter of more than ordinary language. Moreover, metaphor is usually considered a peculiar feature of language alone, which is not a matter of thought or action, but of words. Therefore, many people think that it is possible to get along well without metaphor. We have found, on the contrary, that metaphor is widespread not only in language, but also in thought and action in everyday life. Our usual conceptual system by which we think and act is metaphorical in nature.”

In traditional linguistics, metaphor (“change”, “transference”, “transferred meaning”) is a trope, word or expression used in a figurative sense, based on the general characteristic of comparing one object with another. Metaphor is a figure of speech consisting in the figurative use of words and expressions based on some similarity (analogy) or comparison. Continuing this idea, N.D. Arutyunova defines metaphor as follows: “a trope or speech mechanism consisting in the use of a word denoting a certain class of objects, phenomena, etc. to describe or name an object belonging to another class or the naming of another class. In a broad sense, the term “metaphor” can be applied to any type of use of words used in a figurative sense”.

One of the main features of a metaphor is, of course, its semantic duality, in which the main and secondary meanings coexist, are parallel, the secondary meaning is directly expressed in a specific way in the original meaning, and the secondary meaning can be understood against the background of the original meaning. Thus, the original meaning of the word gives rise to a new, portable meaning that is formed in parallel. From this it can be seen that metaphor is a linguistic structure that is reflected in human thinking, which is the transfer of the characteristic features of a certain object or phenomenon to another object or phenomenon on the basis of similarity.

Metaphor, which is a form of manifestation of secondary nomination, occupies a special place in the creation of a general phraseological meaning. The basis of metaphor is analogy or comparison. A person can compare the unknown notion with the known one, and this shows his/her attitude to objective reality. Since ancient times, language units denoting the most popular concepts and objects of the immediate environment of a person have been subject to metaphorization. Parts of the human body, family ties, animals, plants, materials, clothing items, household items, and natural phenomena play an important role in the emergence of phraseological units.

Phraseological units and set expressions based on human body parts arise based on an analogy with the importance of the human body, in particular, the English idiom *armed to the teeth* can be cited as an example. The expression suggests having weapons (arms) from one’s toes to one’s teeth. E.g. The invading soldiers were armed to the teeth. There was no way the defenders could hope to win.

The eye, another important organ of the human body, is the organ of vision, and it gives rise to many idioms, such as “an apple of one’s eye”, which is defined as a person or thing that is precious or loved above all else. Centuries old, this expression stems from the ancient belief that the pupil of the eye was solid and shaped like an apple. The pupil was considered precious since one could not see without it. E.g. Richard is so attached to his daughter that he would do anything for her. She’s the apple of his eye.

In conclusion, it should be noted that metaphor, as one of the ways of meaning transfer, which is an integral part of the vocabulary of a language, plays a special role in the formation of phraseological units in English.

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